

Thematic maps with mapsf :: CHEAT SHEET

Base map

```
library(mapsf)
# import the sample dataset
mtq <- mf_get_mtg()
# display a base map
mf_map(mtg, col = "orange", border = "white")
# display symbology
mf_map(mtg, var = "POP", type = "prop",
       leg_title = "Population", add = TRUE)
# map layout
mf_layout(title = "Martinique",
          credits = "Source:IGN, 2018")
```


Colors

mapsf can use color palettes from `hcl.colors()`
`mf_get_pal()` is useful to create well-balanced asymmetric diverging palettes

```
mf_get_pal(n = c(7, 2), pal = c("Burg", "Mint"))
```


Symbology

x should be an sf object of polygons, lines, or points.

- Choropleth (ratios)
`mf_map(x = mtq, var = "var", type = "choro", breaks = "quantile")`
- Typology (categories)
`mf_map(x = mtq, var = "var", type = "typo")`
- Proportional Symbols (stocks)
`mf_map(x = mtq, var = "var", type = "prop", inches = .3, symbol = "circle")`
- Graduated Symbols (stocks)
`mf_map(x = mtq, var = "var", type = "grad", pch = 24)`
- Symbols (categories)
`mf_map(x = mtq, var = "var", type = "symb", pch = 21:23)`
- Choropleth Proportional Symbols (stocks - ratios)
`mf_map(x = mtq, var = c("var1", "var2"), type = "prop_choro")`
- Colorized Proportional Symbols (stocks - categ.)
`mf_map(x = mtq, var = c("var1", "var2"), type = "prop_typo")`
- Choropleth Symbols (stocks - categ.)
`mf_map(x = mtq, var = c("var1", "var2"), type = "symb_choro")`
- Raster (single/multi band, continuous, classes, intervals)
`mf_raster(x = raster, type = "continuous")`

Legends

Default legends are plotted with each map.

One can use `mf_legend()` or the `maplegend` package for more customization options.

Map layout

Customization of the layout design

- ① Set a map theme
`mf_theme(background = "#aad3df", mar = c(0, 0, 0, 0))`
- ② Create a shadow effect
`mf_shadow(...)`
- ③ Create a map inset
`mf_inset_on(mtg)`
`mf_map(mtg)`
`mf_inset_off()`
 Use `mf_inset_on(x = "worldmap")` and `mf_worldmap()` to display a globe
- ④ Display a title
`mf_title(...)`

More ?

- Vignettes on the website:
- > How to use themes
 - > How to export maps
 - > How to create inset maps
 - > How to create faceted maps
 - > how to use a custom font family

- ⑤ Display labels
`mf_label(...)`
- ⑥ Display an annotation
`mf_text(...)`
- ⑦ North arrow
`mf_arrow(...)`
- ⑧ Scale bar
`mf_scale(...)`
- ⑨ Credits
`mf_credits(...)`

Export maps

`mf_png()` and `mf_svg()` export maps in PNG and SVG formats. The width/height ratio of the map matches the one of a spatial object.

```
mf_svg(x = mtq, width = 3, filename = "map.svg")
mf_map(mtg)
dev.off()
```


Class intervals

`mf_get_breaks()` uses `classInt` and additional methods (e.g., "Q6", "geom", "arith", "msd" or "ckmeans") to classify continuous variables.

`mf_distr()` can help to select a method for creating class intervals

